

TECHNOLOGY OF DIFFERENTIATED LEARNING AS A FACTOR IN INCREASING COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN LITERATURE CLASSES

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Abstract. *The article discusses the features of organizing the technology of differentiated learning in literature classes, as a factor that improves the quality of specialized education for students.*

Keywords: *technology, differentiated approach, educational process, differentiated training, organization of individual work.*

In the context of socio-economic changes in society, the active introduction of new technologies and fierce competition in the labor market, specialists with independence, initiative and mobility are needed. In this regard, the main goal of modern education today is to form the personality of a future specialist who would be competent, responsible, attentive, able to analyze the situation, provide professional support, strive for self-education, self-development and self-realization in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards of vocational education.

The successful implementation of the goals and objectives of the educational process depends not only on the content of education, methods, techniques and forms of teaching used by teachers, but also on the skillful organization of the entire educational process, which is facilitated by the use of modern educational technologies. Modern innovative technologies in education require a structure of teacher activity, in which all actions are presented in a certain order and integrity. The content, methods, techniques and forms of training should be selected in such a way as to optimize and update the educational process.

One of the best innovative technologies, which is the most effective, is the technology of differentiated learning. The technology is not new, but, nevertheless, it is an effective modern educational technology, since the opportunity to receive a quality education remains one of the most important values of citizens for the formation of an innovative economy of the country, a determining factor in social justice and political stability. The development of the education system provides for individualization, focus on practical skills and basic skills at all stages of the educational process, which is primarily ensured by a differentiated approach to learning.

According to research by I.M. Osmolovskaya, differentiated learning is an approach to learning that takes into account the individual characteristics of groups. Individual learning is the ultimate version of differentiated learning, in which the learning process is built taking into account the characteristics of each student, and not groups. I.M. Osmolovskaya: "Individualization is the ultimate version of differentiation, when the educational process is built taking into account the characteristics not of groups, but of each individual student" [1]. In addition, the importance of personality characteristics as a basis for differentiation may vary at different stages of learning. The necessary conditions for differentiated learning are the following: systematic psychological and pedagogical diagnostics of students and an algorithm for the teacher's activities.

In his book “Modern Educational Technologies” G.K.Selevko [2] notes that differentiated learning is the creation of different learning conditions for different educational institutions, groups in order to take into account the capabilities of their contingent and a complex of psychological, pedagogical, methodological and organizational and managerial measures.

According to Yakimanskaya I.S. [3] a differentiated approach to learning is aimed at the optimal organization of learning through the effective and fruitful learning activities of each student. The task is to determine the right combination of frontal, group and individual work with students in the classroom.

According to I.S. Yakimanskaya, the meaning of differentiation is to determine the most appropriate and effective type of activity, form of work and type of task in the classroom based on knowledge of the individual characteristics of each student (level of development, training, cognitive interest in the subject, characteristics of thinking). When using differentiated learning in the classroom, it is necessary to create conditions for its implementation:

- in-depth study of the typological and individual characteristics of students;
- drawing up a technological map and various issues;
- the ability to “program” the training of various groups of students (Each student);
- organization of the learning process, in which students are given the opportunity to choose the content, type and form of tasks to complete or solve problems;
- provide prompt feedback and create a relaxed atmosphere in classes for students;
- motivate students to succeed;
- positively stimulate students to educational activities; content and form should provide students with opportunities for self-development, self-education and self-expression in the process of acquiring knowledge.

The emergence of a differentiated approach to teaching is associated with the scientific works of such scientists as K.R. Rogers, R.R. May, A.H. Maslow. The principles and basic provisions of differentiation of training were outlined in their works by P.P. Blonsky, I.I. Lesvitsky, B.M. Teplova, I.S. Yakimanskaya et al.

When studying the issue of personal development of students in the context of differentiation of training in the works of researcher E.S. Rabunsky noted that “a differentiated approach is defined as the adaptation of forms and methods of work to the individual characteristics of students” [4]. He dwells in detail on the importance of an individual approach as one of the general pedagogical and didactic principles and gives its rationale:

- the principle of individualized learning differs from other principles of learning in that it emphasizes the need to systematically take into account not only what is social and typical in the personality of each student, but also what is individual and unique;
- each student needs an individual approach. This feature of the principle under consideration is due to the fact that it offers a humane approach that takes into account the individuality of the student;
- an individual approach to the individual is assumed to be a positive, formative and developing principle.[4]

Researcher A.A. Kirsanov characterizes it as follows: “A differentiated approach is a teacher’s special approach to different groups of students, which consists in organizing educational work using methods and techniques that differ in content, volume, and complexity.”[5, p.35]

The concept of differentiation in philosophy has become widespread since scientific works, namely from the “Fundamentals” of Herbert Spencer, who considered differentiation as the main points of the general evolution of matter from simple to complex. There are functional and structural differentiation. In the first case, the range of functions performed by the elements of the developing system expands. In the second case, subsystems that perform specific functions are differentiated within the system. Differentiation can also be understood as highlighting the existence of a number of specialized parts, levels and subsystems.

The famous teacher I.M. Smirnova [86] conducted a comprehensive analysis of the concept of “differentiation of teaching.” She examines psychological, pedagogical and methodological approaches to defining this concept, the existence of which is due to the difference in the objects of the above-mentioned sciences. For example, from a psychological point of view, differentiation is the creation of an appropriate group of students, taking into account all their individual characteristics; from a pedagogical point of view, differentiation is an education system adapted to the inclinations of students; in methodological research, differentiation is the differentiation of the learning process.

Conclusion

The main goal of differentiation of training is to maintain and further develop the individuality of students, the formation of a person who is a unique and original personality.

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